

FRESHWATER GASTROPODS OF THE NORTHWEST OF THE TURKESTAN RIDGE

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Annotation: The article provides data on the malacofauna of freshwater gastropods in the north-west of the Turkestan Range, as well as ecological analysis and altitudinal distribution of mollusks. Faunistic and ecological analysis indicates that the freshwater malacofauna of this region is formed mainly by endemic species.

Keywords: freshwater gastropods, Turkestan Range, malacofauna, ecological analysis, altitude belts.

Annotsiya: Maqolada Turkiston tog‘ tizmasining shimoliy-g‘arbiy qismidagi chuchuk suv qorinoqli mollyuskalarining malakofaunasi, shuningdek, mollyuskalarning ekologik tahlili va balandlik mintaqalari bo‘yicha taqsimlanishi haqida ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan. Faunistik va ekologik tahlil shuni ko‘rsatadiki, bu hududning chuchuk suv malakofaunasi, asosan, endemik turlardan tashkil topgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: chuchuk suv qorinoqli mollyuskalari, Turkiston tog‘ tizmasi, malakofauna, ekologik tahlil, balandlik mintaqalari.

Аннотация: В статье приводятся данные по малакофауне пресноводных брюхоногих моллюсков северо-запада Туркестанского хребта, а также экологический анализ и высотное распределение моллюсков. Фаунистический и экологический анализ свидетельствует о том, что пресноводная малакофауна этого региона сформирована в основном эндемичными видами.

Ключевые слова: пресноводные брюхоногие моллюски, Туркестанский горный хребет, малакофауна, экологический анализ, высотные пояса.

The malacofauna of freshwater gastropods of the northwest of the Turkestan Range, before our research, was studied only by individual collections of Z.I. Izzatullaev [2, 3]. According to Z.I. Izzatullaev, 6 species of freshwater mollusks live in the reservoirs of the northwest part of the Turkestan Range: *Martensamnicola brevicula*, *M. hissarica*, *Bucharamnicola bucharica*, *Lymnaea auricularia*, *L. truncatula* and *Costatella acuta*.

According to our data obtained in recent years, 15 species of freshwater gastropods, belonging to 6 genera and 4 families, live in the water bodies of the northwestern part of the Turkestan Range [4, 5]. Below is the systematic composition of freshwater mollusks in this region.

Type MOLLUSCA

Subtype CONCHIFERA

Class GASTROPODA

Aquatic mollusks

Subclass PECTINIBRANCHIA Blainville, 1814

Order LITTORINIFORMES Pcelintsev, 1963

Family HYDROBIIDAE Stimpson, 1865

Genus *Martensamnicola* Izzatullaev, Sitnikova et Starobogatov, 1985: *Martensamnicola brevicula* (Martens, 1874), *Martensamnicola hissarica* (Shadin, 1950).

Genus *Bucharamnicola* Izzatullaev, Sitnikova et Starobogatov, 1985: *Bucharamnicola bucharica* (Shadin, 1952).

Genus *Sogdamnicola* Izzatullaev, Sitnikova et Starobogatov, 1984: *Sogdamnicola pallida* (Martens, 1874), *Sogdamnicola shadini* Izzatullaev, 1984.

Subclass PULMONATA Guvier, 1817

Order BASOMMATOPHORA Keferstein, 1865

Family LYMNAEIDAE Rafinesque, 1815

Genus *Lymnaea* Lamarck, 1799: *Lymnaea oblonga* (Puton, 1847), *Lymnaea truncatula* (Müller, 1774), *Lymnaea subangulata* (Roffiaen, 1868), *Lymnaea bowelli* (Preston, 1909), *Lymnaea tengriana* Izzatullaev, Kruglov et Starobogatov, 1983, *Lymnaea auricularia* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Lymnaea bactriana* (Hutton, 1849), *Lymnaea rectilabrum* (Annandale et Prashad, 1919).

Family PHYSIDAE Fitzinger, 1833

Genus *Costatella* Dall, 1870: *Costatella acuta* (Draparnaud, 1805).

Family PLANORBIDAE Rafinesque, 1815

Genus *Planorbis* Geoffroy, 1767: *Planorbis tangitarenensis* Germain, 1918.

Ecological analysis of the above-mentioned species showed that the fauna of freshwater gastropods of the Turkestan Range belongs to five (telmatophiles, pelophiles, phytophiles, phytoreophiles, crenophiles) ecological groups and is formed mainly by endemic species of such genera as *Martensamnicola*, *Bucharamnicola*, *Sogdamnicola* and *Lymnaea* (Table 1).

The data in the table show that the largest ecological group in terms of the number of species is the crenophiles (6 species, 40%). The main part of this ecological group is formed by endemic species (*Martensamnicola brevicula*, *M. hissarica*, *Bucharamnicola bucharica*, *Sogdamnicola pallida*, *S. shadini*). The next places are occupied by phytoreophiles and phytophiles (3 species each, 20%), pelophiles (2 species, 13.3%) and telmatophiles (1 species, 6.7%).

Table 1

Distribution of freshwater gastropod molluscs by ecological groups

№	Species name	Telmatophiles	Pelophiles	Phytophiles	Phytoreophiles	Crenophiles
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	<i>Martensamnicola brevicula</i>	-	-	-	-	+
2.	<i>M. hissarica</i>	-	-	-	-	+
3.	<i>Bucharamnicola bucharica</i>	-	-	-	-	+
4.	<i>Sogdamnicola pallida</i>	-	-	-	-	+
5.	<i>S. shadini</i>	-	-	-	-	+
6.	<i>Lymnaea oblonga</i>	-	-	-	+	-
7.	<i>L. truncatula</i>	+	-	-	-	-
8.	<i>L. subangulata</i>	-	-	-	-	+
9.	<i>L. bowelli</i>	-	+	-	-	-
10.	<i>L. tengriana</i>	-	-	-	+	-
11.	<i>L. auricularia</i>	-	-	-	+	-
12.	<i>L. bactriana</i>	-	-	+	-	-
13.	<i>L. rectilabrum</i>	-	+	-	-	-
14.	<i>Costatella acuta</i>	-	-	+	-	-
15.	<i>Planorbis tangitarenensis</i>	-	-	+	-	-
	Total	1 (6,7%)	2 (13,3%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	6 (40%)

In addition, the altitudinal distribution of gastropods was analyzed according to the classification of K. Zakirov [1]. According to this classification, there are 4 types of altitudinal zones: chul (desert, up to 400 m above sea level), adyr (foothills, from 400 to 1200 m above sea level), tau (mountains, from 1200 to 2700 m above sea level) and yaylau (highlands, above 2700 m above sea level) (Table 2).

The data in the table show that freshwater gastropods are mainly distributed in the adyr region (13 species), accounting for 86.66% of all gastropods. In this region, the optimal water temperature and food supply, as well as the year-round flow of springs and springs, have led to the formation of permanent populations. As one ascends from the adyr region to the mountain region, the number of species decreases sharply. This is primarily explained by the decrease in water temperature with increasing altitude and the associated decrease in nutrients. In the adyr region, the number of species also decreases sharply, mainly consisting of representatives of the *Lymnaea* genus.

Table 2

Distribution of freshwater gastropod molluscs by altitudinal regions

№	Species name	chul (desert, up to 400 m)	adyr (foothills, from 400 to 1200 m)	tau (mountains, from 1200 to 2700 m)	yaylau (highlands, above 2700 m)
1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	<i>Martensamnicola brevicula</i>	-	+	+	-
2.	<i>M. hissarica</i>	-	+	+	-
3.	<i>Bucharamnicola bucharica</i>	-	+	-	-
4.	<i>Sogdamnicola pallida</i>	-	+	+	-
5.	<i>S. shadini</i>	-	-	+	-
6.	<i>Lymnaea oblonga</i>	-	+	-	-
7.	<i>L. truncatula</i>	+	+	+	-
8.	<i>L. subangulata</i>	-	+	-	-
9.	<i>L. bowelli</i>	-	-	+	-
10.	<i>L. tengriana</i>	-	+	-	-
11.	<i>L. auricularia</i>	+	+	-	-
12.	<i>L. bactriana</i>	+	+	-	-
13.	<i>L. rectilabrum</i>	-	+	-	-
14.	<i>Costatella acuta</i>	+	+	-	-
15.	<i>Planorbis tangitarensis</i>	-	+	+	-
	Total	4 (26,66%)	13 (86,66%)	7 (46,66%)	-

None of the endemic species of the genus are found in this region. The main reason for this is related to the habitat, which is explained by the absence of springs and springs in this region.

In conclusion, it can be said that the most favorable habitat for gastropod mollusks is the adyr region of the Northwestern Turkestan mountain range.

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